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**Report on the establishment of alliances to
associate with BMS initiatives and
preparations for real-time connections
between ESFRI sites in Europe for data
generation, management and interpretation**

***Workpackage 5
Synergies and Community Building***

ISBE WP5 Coordinators:
Jutta Steinkoetter and James Sharpe

Main responsible authors:
Angela Krueger, Jutta Steinkoetter

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Author(s)	Angela Krüger, Jutta Steinkötter, James Sharpe, Hennig Hermjakob
Project coordinator	Richard Kitney
EC Project Officer	Keji-Alex Adunmo

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Background information

A. Objectives of WP5

The ISBE Work package 5 (WP5), Synergies and Community Building, aims to identify and engage with relevant European stakeholders, including

- researchers who already see themselves as systems biologists
- those, who do not, but would benefit from the ISBE infrastructure
- broader groups of stakeholders like clinical researchers, industry, the media, policy makers, funding organisations and the general public at large
- existing and emerging ESFRI projects in the field of Biological and Medical Sciences (BMS).

One of the goals is therefore to coordinate and communicate developments of the ISBE preparatory phase with ongoing and emerging BMS RI projects and other initiatives, identify the potential of synergies and ultimately, develop collaboration agreements/ Memoranda of Understanding (MoUs), objectives for multi-ESFRI nodes and agreements on accessibility and real-time connections between ISBE and other ESFRI projects.

B. Previous work on Synergies

Previous work of the 'Synergy' part of WP5 focused on the outreach activities to BMS ESFRI and other national and European initiatives. This included the participation and presentation of ISBE at various networking meetings and workshops between research infrastructures, Joint Programme Initiatives (JPIs) and other projects, and the organization of a Synergies Workshop with representation from 12 of the 13 BMS RIs. These activities, their conclusions and immediate outcomes were described in detail in Deliverable D.5.7.

After identifying the overlap and synergies with other infrastructures and initiatives, ISBE WP5 elucidated the perspectives for collaboration agreements between ISBE and potential partners for the exchange of knowledge, the provision of capacities and, harmonisation of experimental and computational approaches. The engagement and interaction efforts of WP5 resulted in a strong representation and participation of ISBE in the CORBEL (COordinated Research Infrastructures Building Enduring Life-science Services), a project in response to the Horizon 2020 (H2020) INFRADEV-4 call. Further details on this project and other WP5 outcomes are described in Deliverable D.5.8.

C. This document

In this deliverable document D.5.9., we report the development of agreements on accessibility and real-time connections between ISBE and other ESFRI projects. Since

most RIs are still developing during their pilot phases and the legal modes of ISBE and many other initiatives are not established yet, the development of agreements and plans on common access and real-time connections was arranged as part of the CORBEL project. CORBEL aims to enhance the integration and harmonisation of actions between all 13 European BMSRIs and will develop cross-RI services through collaborations and joint research activities.

2. General Alliances with BMS initiatives

Coordination and synergy at the transnational level in Europe has been successfully practised over the past 15 years through a number of FP6, FP7 and Horizon2020 programmes, including SysMO, ERASysBio, ERASysAPP, CASyM and ERACoSysMed. The national and European programmes are all based on the teaming-up of systems biology experts with a wide range of other life scientists. This includes development of web-accessible resources and repositories and standardisation efforts. During its preparatory phase ISBE was actively engaging with those projects and intends to build on the solid basis created by these previous and ongoing transnational efforts and expand them to a pan-European level, making resources and expertise accessible to all European scientists.

This is also the case for efforts aiming for the integration and harmonisation between the European BMS RIs, such as BioMedBridges (<http://www.biomedbridges.eu/>), a project that started in 2012 and which is funded through a four-year FP7 grant ending in December 2015. It is a joint effort of twelve biomedical sciences research infrastructures on the ESFRI roadmap, with ISBE as an associated partner. Now being almost at the end of its funding period, BioMedBridges is delivering a series of data integration components that support use-cases spanning the whole of biomedical science, from personalized medicine, through translation between human and mouse phenotypes to fundamental biological questions in structural biology and electron microscopy. The project has also delivered a comprehensive analysis of ethical and data security issues and begins the implementation of services and workflows to address the implementation of these guidelines. Building on these achievements, the CORBEL project – which in contrast to BioMedBridges, includes the full participation of ISBE – will extend and deepen the integration between the infrastructures critical to meet full spectrum of user needs.

3. Real-time connections between ESFRI sites in Europe

The participation of WP5 in strategic and scientific meetings, and in particular the organization of the Synergies workshop, served as a first step for ISBE to establish alliances with BMS initiatives and to specify actions for harmonising data generation, data management and integration approaches.

As follow-up actions, it was agreed to further define how other RIs and projects such as ELIXIR, EuroBioImaging, and BioMedBridges will feed into the ISBE concept to avoid duplication and use synergies.

Thematic interfaces and areas of potential collaborations between ISBE and other initiatives were identified and developed, which set the basis for the elaboration of the scientific use cases as real-time connections between RIs in the CORBEL project.

Specific use cases to build cross-ESFRI BMS infrastructure pipelines

The active partnering with scientific communities and research funding networks through the execution of joint research activities is the focus in CORBEL. The project portfolios include joint BMS RI technical developments as well as use-cases for user-led development of shared services (e.g. partnering with IMI public-private partnership to guide development and test services).

The ISBE WP5 partner MDC will co-lead the CORBEL WP4 'Community Driven Cross-Infrastructure joint research – Bioscience' that has as objectives:

- To establish an infrastructure platform that integrates ESFRI services for life sciences.
- To support scientific research projects that enable the development of shared services between different ESFRI BMS RIs.
- To build the framework for transnational open user access for the sustainable use of the shared services

The CORBEL Workpackage 4 will guide the following use cases:

Use Case 1: A comprehensive approach to predicting and modeling the phenotypic implications of mutations and of genome-sequence, lifestyle and ambition differences between individuals, and to validate the predictions in *in vivo* models.

The aims of this use case are (i) to provide a set of integrative models with associated data and technologies for life scientists to relate genotype to

phenotype and (ii) to establish a pipeline for users to produce such integrative models. The objective is to establish corresponding research (i) and service (ii) pipelines between RIs. The integration of the ESFRIs will be implemented by research projects which aim to predict specific aspects of phenotypes from individual information. The pipelines will empower users to address main research topics, such as systems and personalized medicine, rare diseases, metabolic and inflammatory diseases, cancer, precision biotechnology and modern non-recombinant agriculture. With this, there will be imminent impact for translational research and the health and biotechnology industry. There will be intense communication and collaboration between use cases as well as with the medical use case portfolio (WP3) to ensure alignment between RIs and translation from biological to medical applications. Legal and ethical issues for data exchange and protection in trans-national research collaborations will be addressed in WP7.

The RIs will contribute the following (through provision or connecting):

BBMRI-ERIC (BRFAA, Athens): provision of biological samples to be analysed; provision of data together with the samples integrated into computational models (with MDC and EMBL-ELIXIR);

ELIXIR (EMBL-EBI, Hinxton): provision of curated reference datasets and annotations, storage of data; provision of computational models that make the storage data predictive (with MDC);

ISBE (MDC Berlin, VUA Amsterdam): computational analysis and integration of genomic, transcriptomics, epigenomics, metabolomics and physiomics data; models from genome information and organism function; integration of models to complete the trajectory from genes to whole organism function and disease; molecular, physiological and multi-scale modelling approaches; diverse model types and modelling methodologies (e.g. Boolean, Bayesian, Petri-Nets, ODE, PDE, stochastic); model driven experimental design; model-associated data integration; provision of models on samples (with BBMRI-ERIC), imaging experiments (with Euro-Biolmaging), mouse strains (with INFRAFRONTIER GmbH) and stored data sets (with EMBL-ELIXIR)

Euro-Biolmaging (CRG, Barcelona): small animal imaging and fluorescence microscopy; (together with ISBE) provision of computational and data analysis models together with access;

INFRAFRONTIER (HMGU, Munich): provision of mouse models and data to test/validate models; (together with ISBE) provision of computational models for each mouse strain and data set provided.

Use Case 2: A comprehensive approach to determine and validate experimentally, model *in silico* and predict the pharmacological and toxicological effects of chemicals on biological model systems, based on information ranging from the 3D-atomic structures of compound target interactions and individual genomic information to the response of whole cell/organisms to those compounds.

The aim of this use case is to build a seamless workflow with the experimental and virtual services of ESFRI BMS and complementary RIs that contribute to the quantitative analysis, description, comprehension and modelling of the effects of chemical substances on biological systems (pharmacology). A broad variety of major research topics in the field of health, food and environment that are in line with EU-funding strategy to solve societal challenges can be addressed. This includes most obviously the field of medical drug research (target validation, drug repurposing strategies, synergistic drug combinations and drug adverse effects, toxicology, safety, reduction of attrition rates, biomarker discovery) but extends seamlessly to the impacts of chemicals on veterinary, agricultural and environmental applications exploiting target structure similarities. There is a significant cross-talk to the other use cases as well as those in the medical sciences; the participating RIs will assure a tight alignment with this pharmacology workflow.

The different RI's contributing to this Use Case will address the following areas:

ELIXIR (EMBL-EBI): Building curated reference datasets and annotations; tools for big data and literature mining and visualization, bio- and chem-informatics support, storage of data.

EU-OPENSREEN (FVB): Generation and provision of data on chemical structures with biological activities from high-throughput screening experiments; mode of action studies

INSTRUCT (CIRMMP): Generation and provision of 3D structural data focused on macromolecular interactions *in vitro* and *in vivo*. Development of methods for the description of the dynamic aspects of interaction and their impact on molecular recognition; Integrative approaches for the generation of structure based interactomics information.

ISBE (VU/VUmc, Amsterdam): Integration of data through association with models; multi-scale and multilevel modelling of cellular and whole body networks; omics technologies and big data generation; making data predictive of pharmacology and toxicology through models, connecting PKPD with molecular systems biology

Euro-BioImaging (EMBL-HD): Image-based read-out technologies of cellular/organismal responses

EMBRC (SZN): Access to marine model organism (see use case 4)

MIRRI (DSMZ): Access to cell cultures and microbes, genomes.

INFRAFRONTIER (HMGU): Access to genotyped mouse models.

Use Case 3: A comprehensive approach to structure function analysis of the molecular machinery based on integrated access to structure determination methods of isolated protein complexes correlated with functional and *in situ* imaging methods and support the integration of the resulting data from the molecular to the cellular scale of biological organization in order to make functional predictions that can be validated.

Together, Euro-BioImaging, INSTRUMENT, ISBE and ELIXIR will establish an integrative access and service pipeline to methods from the nano- to the micrometer scale including atomic resolution three-dimensional (3D) information, 3D maps from electron and soft-xray microscopies, correlative light-electron microscopy, super-resolution microscopy, functional imaging, data repositories, data standards, quantitative imaging analysis and data integration. The aim of the use case is to start making possible an integrative modelling approach to the understanding of protein complex functions in health, disease and after (drug) treatment.

The different RI's contributing to this Use Case will address the following areas:

Euro-BioImaging (EMBL Heidelberg, UMCU Utrecht, ICFO Barcelona): Correlative light-electron microscopy, super-resolution microscopy, functional imaging methods, image data standards and repositories.

ELIXIR (EMBL-EBI, Hinxton): Interlinked data repositories for image data types with different resolution.

INSTRUMENT (CSIC Madrid): Molecular resolution EM, EM image data standards, atomic-level 3D structural and interaction information, software tools for data integration together with ELIXIR.

ISBE (DKFZ Heidelberg): Quantitative analysis, data integration and modelling for functional predictions.

Use Case 4: A comprehensive approach for access to harmonised marine metazoan developmental model databases, integrating genomic, transcriptomics, and morphological information, also through *in silico* models, and building on existing community resources.

This use case aims for a complementary set of selected marine metazoan models for developmental and cell biology: 1) to set up integrated databases combining sequence and imaging data via pipelines linking EMBRC-ERIC, Euro-Biolmaging, EMBL-ELIXIR and ISBE as user-friendly entry portals for both established and new users. These will be designed to allow integration with computational models of development, and future integration also of gene manipulation phenotypes and chemical response data. 2) to provide access to biological material as well as functional genomics and imaging capabilities for testing and exploitation of these models in selected pilot user test cases. The Use Case is geared to provide advanced understanding of biological mechanisms underlying disease, through promoting the use of diverse and experimentally accessible alternative model species.

Approach

EMBRC, ELIXIR and Euro-Biolmaging will work together to develop pipelines to establish harmonised marine metazoan developmental model databases integrating genomic, transcriptomic and morphological data. Pipelines for the integration of functional genomic and chemical treatment data will also be planned. The database suite will build on existing community resources (genome, gene expression and imaging data) from the EMBRC partners and their collaborators, notably P. Lemaire (Montpellier) who developed the ANiSEED database framework for ascidian development (<http://www.aniseed.cnrs.fr/>), which is currently being adopted and adopted by EMBRC laboratories for three other model species. The initial database suite will cover 4 marine models developed by European researchers characterised by complementary modes of embryogenesis: ascidian (*Phallusia*, *Ciona*), amphioxus (*Branchiostoma*), sea urchin (*Paracentrotus*) and jellyfish (*Clytia*). These species form a complementary and powerful set of experimental model species. The database suite will serve a central curated repository and will allow a wide user base in biological and biomedical sciences to explore *in silico* the potential of alternative models to address specific biological questions. Access to the biological material and experimentation facilities including imaging will then be facilitated by joint EMBRC/ Euro-Biolmaging/ ELIXIR/ interfaces.

The RIs will contribute the following (through provision or connecting):

EMBRC (CNRS/UPMC, St Andrews, SZN): Marine organisms and facilities for experimentation, 4D imaging, database information.

ELIXIR (EMBL-EBI): Harmonising Standards, Nomenclature, Data integration, Database interoperability, Strategy development for hosting and curation.

Euro-BiolImaging (EMBL-HD): Combined access to advanced imaging and some marine model species at EMBL, Pipelines for acquisition, processing and integration of imaging data into databases.

EU-OPENSREEN (FVB): identification of users with needs of assay systems with particular characteristics accessible in marine models (e.g. cilia beating, chromosome disjunction...)

ISBE (VU Amsterdam): access to and data-integration with computational models of marine organisms.

4. Outcome

The interfaces between the BMS RIs are fundamental for the flow of projects through the technology platforms. Harmonisation of infrastructure user access procedures, ethical advice and assessment and legal documents is critical for effective infrastructure utilisation and will deliver direct and tangible benefits for users. The core strategy of CORBEL is to deliver and stress-test this shared platform of shared services and scientific connections through a portfolio of representative, user-focussed exemplar projects and joint research efforts.

Ultimately the outcomes of this coordinated and sustained effort will be that:

- Users, no matter which infrastructure they first approach, will benefit from a coherent set of processes and collaborative interfaces that support access and use of advanced research tools, samples and facilities.
- Funders and other stakeholders will benefit from effective engagement mechanisms and overview of cost-effective research infrastructure services, harmonised legal and ethical expert services
- Society will benefit from a focused, pan-European, innovation effort that will drive industry engagement and delivery of societal value based on excellent scientific research.